

A Critical Study of Teacher Education Programmes in Manipur

Chirom Rebika Devi

The present study attempts to explore the development of teacher education in Manipur since independence, to study the present conditions and status of teacher education programmes with regard to pre-service, in-service, primary teacher education, secondary teacher education, to study the curriculum and its implementation in the Teacher Education Institutions with regard to physical facilities, teachers qualification, time-table, practice teaching, teaching method, evaluation and teacher's professional attitude. It also explores the main problems of teacher education of elementary and secondary school teachers in the state and to make suggestions for the improvement of teacher education programme. The study is undertaken in one SCERT, five out of eight DIET and five B.Ed. colleges and of their teachers will constitute the sample of the study. For the study of the present conditions, status and problems the investigator adopted Normative-Survey Method of research by developing appropriate tools and techniques of data collection and visiting the institutions personally. An analysis and interpretation is made from the data collected through information sheets and questionnaire about the five B.Ed. colleges and five DIETs of teacher education in Manipur. Specific immediate measures needed to be taken up by the Government to remove the problems of teacher education and producing quality teachers to achieve qualitative improvement in education at any level in Manipur are suggested.

Keywords: Teacher Education, DIET, B.Ed, Teacher Educator, Student Teacher

Introduction

Education, according to Indian tradition, is not merely a means to earn a living; nor is it only a nursery of thought or a school for citizenship. It is an initiation into the life of spirit, a training of human soul in pursuit of truth and the practice of virtue. Aristotle, however, held that education exists exclusively to develop man's intellect in a world of reality which men can know and understand.

National Policy on Education (NPE) 1986 has envisaged a multifaceted approach to the overhauling of the training of school teachers. Creation of new objectives of teacher's education occupies an important place in the new policy. Quality education of

Chirom Rebika Devi is Lecturer at Modern College, Imphal East, Manipur, India.

the State is concerned, there is a need to understand the conditions and status of the existing institutions providing teacher education of all level for both pre-service and in-service. It is also necessary to assess in the light of the objectives of NPE 1986 and POA 1992 the conditions and status trends of teacher education programme in Manipur. In keeping with this view, the investigator undertakes the study on the institutes of teacher education imparting elementary and secondary school teachers in the State.

Development of Teacher Education in Manipur

The formation of Teacher Education in India on modern line was laid in the last part of 17th century by the European and Danish millionaires by setting up many schools. Following the recommendation of Wood's Dispatch of 1854, many teachers training institutions were established in different parts of India. Hunter Commission of 1882, had also emphasised the importance of teacher education. As Lord Curzon's education policy encouraged the establishment of training institution for the secondary schools, there were 15 teacher training institutions in 1912, giving training to 1,400 secondary school teachers. Subsequent education Commission viz, the Radhakrishnan Commission of 1948, Mudallar Commission of 1952, the Kothari Commission of 1976 – all have given serious thoughts to the improvement of teacher education in India.

In Manipur the need for giving training to teachers was felt as early as in 1906. Around this time the Department of Education organised a training course for teachers for four months for the improvement of the method of teaching. Twenty primary school teachers attended the courses, of which nine teachers passed after the completion of the course. This was the beginning of teacher education in Manipur. Giving training to the secondary school teacher began in 1928, when one of the teachers of Johnstone High School, Imphal was deputed to undergo B.T. training outside Manipur. This marked the beginning of training programme for secondary schools teachers. In 1932 a seminar was organised on the methods of training various subjects and the teachers who attended the seminar were greatly benefited.

After 1947, the State Government took keen interest in teacher training programmes. A humble beginning of training the primary and middle school teachers in Manipur was made in 1952-53, by starting normal training institute at Imphal.

So far the education of the secondary school teachers is concerned it was done by opening B.T. section in the Dhanamanjuri College in 1959. Before this, the teachers were sent on deputation for training outside Manipur. Along with B.T. section, there were C.T. (Certificate of Teaching) classes in the composite of D.M. College, Imphal. The B.T. course was intended for graduate teachers. C.T. course was for the undergraduate teachers. C.T. course was closed after two years and it was absorbed as Basic Training Course in the Basic Training College which was established in 1961 at Imphal.

The B.T. classes at D.M. College were converted into full-fledged Training College (P.G.T.). The College was initially affiliated to Gauhati University and later on it was transferred to Manipur University in 1980.

To clear the back-log of the untrained teachers in Manipur, the State Institute of Education (SIE) Manipur, took up the task of training teachers from 1980 onwards. A sub-centre for teaching-cum-correspondence B.Ed. course was set up by S.I.E., Manipur under the Regional College of Education, Bhubaneswar.

B.Ed. elementary course has also been started for the teachers of primary to high school level by SIE, Manipur from 1983. The sub-centre imparts training to 250 teachers a year. The B.Ed. (Secondary) and B.Ed. (Elementary) courses run by SIC, Manipur are equivalent to the courses run by the Utkal University, Orissa. Secondary Teacher Education or B.Ed. is again affiliated to Manipur University after its establishment in 1980. Now, the state is having six B.Ed. Colleges for providing Secondary Teacher Education to both pre-service and in-service teachers. B.Ed. teachers education has also been taken up by IGNOU study Centre, D.M. College of Teachers Education, Imphal under distance mode to help in clearing the backlog of untrained Secondary Teachers of Manipur. For imparting training to Hindi Teachers of Primary Schools, the Government of Manipur established one Hindi Teacher's Training Institute in 1953 with the intake capacity of 40 and Hindi Teacher's College in 1975 with the provision of giving training to 30 teachers.

Two more Secondary Teacher Training Institutions were established under private management as Kanan Devi Memorial College of Education, Pangei, Imphal East District and Thokchom Ibotombi Institute of Teacher Training at Bishnupur. The recognition of the latter institute has been withdrawn by NCTE from the academic session 2002-2003 for violation of norms. But it has been restored since 2004-05 academic session.

The existing Elementary Teacher Training Institutions like Basic Training Institutes (BTI's) and Basic Training College (BTC) were reorganised into District Institute of Education and Training (DIETs) and the secondary teacher training institute; Post-Graduate Training College was upgraded into College of Teacher Education. The college has been renamed as Dhanamanjuri College of Teacher Education (DMCTE) re-linking its root to the erstwhile D.M. College where the Department of B.T. was first open in 1959. The State Institute of Education (SIE) was re-organised and upgraded into SCERT under a separate directorate of its own. Under this umbrella six DIETs are operating at Imphal, Kakching, Moirang, Churachanpur, Senapati and Chandel since 1990.

Two more DIETs have been established in two districts namely DIET of Ukhrul and DIET of Tamenglong. One more DIET has been under processed at Imphal East District. For the Secondary school teachers, two more private colleges of education have also been established during 2002-2004, Trinity Teacher Training College and R.K. Sanatombi Devi College of Teacher Education. B.Ed. teachers education has also been taken up at the IGNOU Study Centre and D.M. College of Teacher Education to help in clearing the backlog of untrained Secondary Teachers of Manipur.

Present condition and status

Teacher Education for pre-primary school teachers

Government of Manipur established one pre-primary school teachers training institute at Imphal under the recommendation of State Commission of Education Report 1992. After the implementation of the programme of early childhood care and Education under NPE 1986, a number of Pre-primary School Teachers' Training Institutions have been established in Manipur until now.

There are about 5 Pre-Primary School Teachers' Training Institutes under private management in the state.

Pre-Primary teacher education programme in Manipur is at the initial stage. The training centres run by the State Government and NGOs give on-job training courses to Anganwadi workers and helpers. The Central Social Welfare Board organises orientation courses at regular interval for the benefit of Anganwadi helpers. Primary school teacher working in the institutions in different districts can join the in-service teacher training programmes conducted by DIETs. It aims to provide the latest methods of teaching and learning. Information technology is included in the new syllabus and text books for class I-V have been introduced from the session in 2004-05 and the teachers are to be oriented to acquaint them the knowledge of teaching new text books.

Teacher Education for Elementary school teachers

There are eight District Institutes of Education and Training (DIETs) in the 9 districts of Manipur which provide teacher education of both pre-service and in-service teachers of elementary education with intake capacity of 130 for one year course.

Each branch is to be headed by a senior lecturer with sufficient member of lectures depending upon the work load of the Branch.

SCERT is conducting pre-service teacher education programme intake capacity of 50 pre-service candidates and 80 in-service candidates. The duration of two courses, CETEd (Certificate course in Elementary Teacher Education) for in-service and DETEd (Diploma in Elementary Teacher Education) for pre-service elementary school teachers are 6 (six) months and 2 (two) years respectively as envisaged by in the DIETs Scheme.

The table given shows the different location of DIETs in Manipur and their establishment and number of trainees in both pre-service and in-service.

Table: 1. Establishment of Diet Institution

Sl.No.	Name of Institution	Year of Establishment	Number of Trainees		Total
			Pre-service	In-service	
1.	DIET,Imphal	1991	50	80	130
2.	DIET,C.C.Pur	1992	50	80	130
3.	DIET,Kakching	1992	50	80	130
4.	DIET,Moirang	1995	50	80	130
5.	DIET,Senapati	1997	50	80	130
6.	DIET,Chandel	2002	50	80	130
7.	DIET,Tamenglong	2002	50	80	130
8.	DIET,Ukhrul	2002	50	80	130

Source: Institution Records

Teacher Education for Physical Education teachers

Physical Education has become an integral part of school subject in the primary, middle and high school. To teach the subject, trained teachers are needed. At present there is no training institute of physical education to prepare the teachers for the subject. The Direc-

torate of Physical Education, Sports and Youth Affairs deputed the teachers to different institutions at Gwalior, Madras, Patna and Amravati. Some candidates also seek admission in the institutions mentioned above on their own. Recently, Manipur University has introduced Physical Education as a subject in the Three Year Degree Course of Studies in some colleges. The colleges which impart physical education as a subject are Biramangol College, D.M. College of Science and Kakching Khunou College. Graduates with Physical Education as a subject from Manipur University can be the teachers of Physical Education in the Schools of Manipur.

Teacher Education for Secondary school teacher

There are six colleges of Teachers Education at present in Manipur with one Government management including HTTI. All the six colleges are located in the valley districts of Manipur. These colleges provide B.Ed course.

Table 2. Establishment of B.Ed. Institution

Sl. No.	Name of the Institutions	Year of Estd.	Management	Course Provided	Intake capacity
1.	D.M.College of Teacher Education	1972	Govt.	B.Ed., M.Ed.	230 & 25
2.	Kanan Devi College of Teacher Education	1992	Private	B.Ed.,	100
3.	Thokchom Ibotombi Institute of Education & Training	1997	Private	B.Ed.,	100
4.	Trinity Teachers Training College	2001	Private	B.Ed.,	100
5.	R.K.Sanatombi Devi College of Education	2002	Private	B.Ed., M.Ed.	150 & 25

Source – College Record

These colleges got recognition from the National Council for Teachers Education (NCTE) and Manipur University become the examining body by framing curriculum and syllabus under the direction of NCTE.

Secondary Teacher Education programmes are taken up by the Teacher Training Colleges providing one year B.Ed. course under norms and guidelines of NCTE. The State is having Six B.Ed. Colleges for providing Secondary Teacher Education to both pre-service and in-service teachers. B.Ed. teachers education has also been taken up at the IGNOU Study Centre and D.M.. College of Teacher Education to help in clearing the backlog of untrained Secondary Teachers of Manipur.

It is the over-all responsibility of the Education Department for teacher education through its agency, the SCERT. There are eight DIETs in the State functioning under the direct control of the SCERT. There are 154 Block Resource Centres (BRCs) and 420 experi-

enced teachers have been positioned as Block Resource Persons (BPPs), 156 Cluster Resource Centres (CRCs) functioning under the direct control of SCERT, SSA and DIETs respectively.

Main problem of Teacher Education of Elementary and Secondary school teachers in Manipur

1. Problems of Selecting Candidates for Education: There is a great problem of selecting teacher candidates both for in-service and pre-service due to insincerity of the authorities.

2. Problem of Qualitative Improvement: The present teacher institutions of DIET's and College of teacher education lack quality in various aspects like poor quality of teaching, outdated methods of teaching, incompetent teachers, lack of facilities, bulkiness of syllabus, short term courses, defective examination system, faulty admission policy and defective practice of teaching programme.

3. Backlog of Untrained Teachers: There is lack of clearing backlog of untrained teachers both in elementary and secondary school teachers. At this present rate of producing trained teachers in Manipur, it will take a decade to clear the backlog of teachers in Manipur due to the large number of untrained teachers. A possible suggestion is that Manipur University can open a department for correspondence education for Secondary School teachers. Also the present intake capacity of the training institutes can be increased to solve the problem of backlog of untrained teachers. According to 2001 census there are 11283 untrained teachers at the Elementary Schools.

4. Incompetent Teachers: Most of the teachers of the newly establishment DIET's and College of Teacher Education are very incompetent in teaching and profession. The teachers of college of education also lack innovativeness and efficiency. Due to these problems the quality of teachers education is degraded and now it is just for providing certificate.

5. Establishment of Sub-Standard Private B.Ed. Colleges: In the commercial basis more sub-standard private colleges of teacher have been established.

6. Non-implementation of training: There is non-implementation of training or teaching received from the training institutions. There is ineffectiveness of training of teachers.

7. Problem of improper planning: There is no proper planning of teacher education in Manipur. Many pitfalls were found in the working of the existing teacher educations such as the Government established Basic Training Institute and Colleges for training the teacher. Many crafts are introduced and craft instructors are appointed. But the Government is not able supply raw materials, and equipments required for the crafts. There are no proper laboratories in the institutions and as such teaching is mechanical. Moreover, the training received by the teachers is not utilised in the schools when they return to their parent posts after the completion of the course of training. This was the condition when BTIs and BTCs were functioning.

The newly-started sub-centres of B.Ed.(Elementary) and B.Ed. (Secondary) run by SIE have no buildings and neither properly staffed nor properly equipped. Practice teaching is carried out only in name; there are no laboratory facilities for practical work. Practice teaching, and the contact programmes are far from satisfaction. There is dearth

of qualified and experienced resource persons. Under such conditions, it is obvious that the training given is below the standard. Government has to provide these basic requirements in the teacher training centres.

8. Poor infrastructure of the institutes of teacher education is also there.

Objectives of the study

- To trace out the development of Teacher Education in Manipur since Independence.
- To study the present conditions and status of the Teacher Education programmes with regard to Pre-service, In-service, Primary Teacher Education, and Secondary Teacher Education.
- To study the curriculum and its implementation in the Teacher Education Institutions with regard to Physical Facilities, Teachers qualification, Time-Table, Practice Teaching, Teaching Method, Evaluation and Teacher's professional attitude, etc.
- To explore the main problems of teacher education of elementary and secondary schools teachers in the State.
- To make suggestions for the improvement of teacher education programme.

Baseline Survey

The study has been conducted five DIETs, five B.Ed. Colleges teacher education and one SCERT of General Studies excluding Hindi Teacher Training College. The study will cover only the teacher training institutions for Teacher Education Programme meant for the training of Pre-primary, Primary, Upper primary and Secondary School Teachers of Manipur. Not only Post-Graduate studies in education but also B.Ed. course at the IGNOU study centre, Imphal has also been excluded. The respondents of the present investigation are also selected from different areas of Manipur.

Method of the study

The proposed study on the institutes of Teacher Education will be employed partly historical method in focusing the developmental trends of Teacher Education in the State through secondary sources of data like books, documents, reports and thesis. For the study of the present conditions, status and problems the investigator will adopt normative-survey method of research by developing appropriate tools and techniques of data collection and visiting to the institutions personally.

Sample of study

One S.C.E.R.T., five out of eight DIETs and five B.Ed. Colleges and their teachers will constitute the sample of the study.

Tools used

In the proposed study the investigator will employ the following tools and techniques.

- (i) A questionnaire for the teachers and information schedule for the college.
- (ii) Interview through personal contact of the principal, managing committee, director of education, teachers, student-teachers and other authorities.
- (iii) Observation through field study.

(iv) Problem check list will be prepared.

Data Collection

The data from one S.C.E.R.T., five out of eight DIET and five B.Ed. Colleges, their teachers and students were collected by conducting personal interviews. The details of the curriculum and its implementation in the teacher education institutions physical facilities, teachers qualification, time-table, practice teaching, teaching method, evaluation and teacher's professional attitude etc. were collected with the help of pre-designed questionnaire for the teachers and information schedule for the college. Opinion of teacher educators and student teacher for the teacher education programme has also been obtained. The data have been processed and tabulated using SPSS package. The analysis of the data has been attempted as qualitative and quantitative on the basis of the nature of data.

Main findings

- Most of the Teacher Education Colleges has adequate number of rooms with auditorium or conference hall except Thokchom Ibotombi Institute of Teacher Education and Training and also have good physical conditions and big and spacious campus.
- Infrastructure of the Colleges are almost adequate with good sanitation except Health and Medical Services, Bus service, post office, bank and book store. Teaching Aids or Audio Visual Aids and Internet/fax facilities are available with some colleges. Two colleges namely Kanan Devi Memorial College of Education and Thokchom Ibotombi Institute of Teacher Education & Training have CAI (Computer Assisted Instruction) facilities. There is lack of employing computer and educational technology application in most of the colleges.
- Almost all the colleges have the same schedule for practice teaching with same duration and have own practice teaching school in the campus for B.Ed. course in the state.
- Most of the Colleges of teacher education aims at providing quality teacher education programmes in the State in order to upgrade the standard of school education in general.
- Four private colleges of teacher education have faced financial problems like low salary of the teaching and non-teaching staffs. No scope for improving the status of the teaching communities, autocratic nature of administration of the managing committee, lack of research facilities and continuation of studies, etc. are the main problems of the five colleges of teacher education.
- Most of the teacher educators are taking six period of class in a week in the afternoon with two working hours per day. One practical class has been performed in a week using sufficient teaching aids in classes.
- More than three colleges are well equipped for training materials. It has been identified that the existing demonstration classes are insufficient.
- The teaching method taught in training programme is the effective using audio-visual aids in teaching. Most of the teacher educators have submitted feedback report.
- Most of the teacher educators are satisfied with the evaluation system of the in-service and pre-service secondary teacher education.
- Majority of teacher educators have taken internal assessment and class test regularly.

- Most of teacher educators participated in seminars/workshops and conferences.
- Most of the student teachers have some problems in getting admission to the teacher education course.
- Majority of the student teachers acknowledges the existence of some defects of the existing examination and evaluation system.
- All five DIETs of education have elementary level of education and provide CETEd course with an intake capacity of 80 seats each; and DETEd course with an intake capacity of 50 seats each. The duration of CETEd course and DETEd course is 6 months and 2 years respectively.
- The DIETs of teacher education have more female candidates than male candidates in both CETEd and DETEd course, and female candidates have more positive attitude towards teaching profession with preference to teaching jobs.
- Majority of the DIETs have faced some problem like lack of academic infrastructure, lack of hostel facility for students, lack of staff quarter, no irregular payment of salary, and all the staff are contractual employees.
- Most of the teacher educators of DIETs took a minimum of four periods of class in a week in the afternoon with two working hours per day. Maximum two period of practical class have been performed in a week using sufficient teaching aids in teaching classes.
- It is expressed by most of the teacher education of DIETs that there is no difference between examination and evaluation system conducted by SCERT.
- Majority of teacher educators have positive attitude regarding teacher professional attitude.
- Most of the DIETs institutes have inadequate infrastructure.
- Majority of the student teachers expressed that there are some defects of existing examination and evaluation system and they have medium job facility.
- Most the student teachers have expressed that there is poor quality of education programme in their institution and teacher education programme is in great demand by the educated youths in Manipur.

Suggestion for the improvement

- Improvement of professional development of teachers' educators is highly essential in the State.
- All types of teacher education programme from pre primary, primary, secondary and post graduate should rest with the university.
- Competent, efficient and dedicated teacher-educators should be appointed and full freedom to be given to teacher educators and student teachers and teachers at school level to do whatever they think fit while implementing new TEP.
- Reform of curriculum and syllabus is also urgently needed and teacher education programmes should be redesigned to respond to the school curriculum renewal process and in accordance with the state and regional context in which they are situated.
- Modern techniques of teaching through ICT and evaluation should be adopted.
- Visiting of eminent teacher-educators from the national agencies such as NCTE, NCERT should be encouraged.
- Teacher Education Programmes should be ideally of five years duration after the comple-

tion of 10+2 level of school education in the state.

- An integrated model for teacher education could comprise of core components that would be common to all teacher education programmes (pre-primary, elementary and secondary) followed by specialisation of professional development specific to the stage of education.
- Teacher education programmes should be redesigned to respond to the school curriculum renewal process and in accordance with the state and regional context in which they are situated.
- Workshop, seminar, orientation programme conference and refresher course should be organised to initiate discussion and devise possible strategies to operationally the redesigned teacher education and development from time to time.

Conclusion

To conclude, the five B.Ed colleges of teacher education have been doing their best to impart effective programmes of teacher education. Many developmental programmes have been taken up with regard to infrastructure and other physical conditions of the colleges. Though, it is very sad to learn that the teacher of private colleges of teacher education received a meager amount of remuneration as consolidated pay which is humiliating teaching profession in the State. The managing committee should keep in their mind that teachers are like the machine and gardener of the factory or a farm, if the machines are not properly working the factory will die. Keeping with this view, the managing committee, while taking up any developmental programmes, they should consider that increasing teachers pay and salary is also a part of total development which is of utmost importance. They should not think that teacher education is one of the commercial enterprises.

Further, it has been observed that majority of the DIETs do not have physical and infrastructural facilities, laboratory equipment, library facilities, electronic equipments, computer education, boundary walls, etc. The deficiencies in the physical and infrastructural facilities can be met over a period of time if the central government provides necessary funds to meet the deficiencies.

To eliminate/root out such problems, a specific immediate measure needs to be taken up from the government. Thus, producing quality teachers has become a pre-requisite to achieve qualitative improvement in education at any level. Both the central and the state governments should come forward to enhance the budgetary allocation on teacher education and to recruit highly qualified persons as teacher educator.

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